

The Operation of Barangay Peace and Order Council of Santa Maria, Isabela, Philippines

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Abstract :- Executive Order 309 dictates the operation of the Barangay Peace and Order Council to heighten the efficiency of Municipal Peace and Order Council by extending its membership and the addition of its infrastructure in the barangay level. This study assessed the operation of the Barangay Peace and Order Council of Santa Maria, Isabela. Variables such as the functionality of the barangay peace and order council, participation of the council sectors in the peace and order program, implementation of peace and order ordinances, and community satisfaction on the performance of the council are investigated. Using descriptive design, data gathered from sixty barangay peace and order council members and eighty citizens of Santa Maria, Isabela, Philippines were analyzed using arithmetic mean. Results showed that the barangay peace and order council of Santa Maria, Isabela is functional concerning organization, meetings, policies, plans & budget, and accomplishment. Likewise, the council members participate in the implementation of the peace and order programs. Furthermore, findings displayed that the peace and order ordinances are implemented in the whole municipality and the community residents are satisfied on the performances of the barangay peace and order council.

Keywords:- *Functionality, Implementation, Participation, Peace and Order Council, Ordinance, Satisfaction.*

I. INTRODUCTION

The goal of peace, justice, and strong institutions is one of the sustainable development objectives set by the United Nations. This underscores the importance of peaceful societies in facilitating sustainable development. Peace serves as a measure of the success of the United Nations in improving the living conditions of all individuals both now and for future generations, while also protecting the world. The global community underlines the importance of peace and justice, advocating for more robust legal systems that will uphold laws and strive towards a more peaceful and just environment for everyone.

Peace is both global and inseparable due to it is essential for humanity's survival, and ensuring peace and security for people is crucial for promoting economic growth, social stability, and political integrity. Furthermore, studies have indicated that in the Philippines, the enforcement of community peace and order and public safety (POPS) is strictly adhered to by the government and is largely implemented; however, there were notable differences when barangays were categorized into various groups (Mangilimutan, Mejica, & Caelian, 2020).

Likely, Adonis S. B., (2021) assessed the employment and impact of peace and order initiatives alongside the governance approaches of the Punong Barangay in General Santos City, Philippines, focusing on vision and mission, barangay strategies, policies, and programs. The findings indicated that the effectiveness of program execution is high, and the leadership style was identified as democratic.

The write-ups of Aydinan, B & Ayeo-Eo, P. (2020) presented that the mainstream of the barangay peace and order initiatives are only moderately met according to the views of the inhabitants. Therefore, it is suggested that barangay officials, along with all relevant personnel including the lead of the barangay enforcers, the enforcers themselves, and barangay staff, collaborate to strengthen the peace and order initiatives within the community. This should be achieved through thorough planning and clearly defined strategies within the country's lowermost political unit.

In addition, Domingo Jr B.C., (2020) publicized that the solution to the challenges of criminality is the contribution of the members of the peace and order council in the effective operation of the POCs POPS Plan. In addition, the actions of the POC is relevant on the realization of the government activities to addressing problems related to crime. Thus, strive in conveying criminological knowledge to reliable public safety and peace and order strategy by the government policy makers is suggested.

Executive Order No. 309 requiring the operation of the Barangay Peace and Order Councils was shaped because of the government's acknowledgment of the need to augment the efficacy of the Peace and Order Council (POC) in its mission in crime prevention and suppression through the intensification of its membership and the extension of its infrastructure until the barangay level. Moreover, Executive Order 366 which amended Executive Order 309 mandates that in every Barangay there shall be the establishment of Barangay Peace and Order Committee that shall work as the executing arm at the barangay level of the City/Municipal Peace and Order Council. Such Committee shall be composed of the Punong Barangay as Chairman; the Sangguniang Kabataan chairperson; a public school teacher; the lupon tagapamayapa members; a barangay tanod; interfaith groups' representative; a senior citizen; a PNP officer, and at least three (3) members of existing barangay-based anti-crime or neighborhood watch groups or an NGO representative well-known in the community. Likewise, the same law stipulates the functions and responsibilities of the Barangay Peace and Order Committee to embrace the following: Monitoring and coordinating the enactment of peace and order programs and projects at the barangay; monitoring, synchronizing and supervising the operation of all community-based anti-crime movements within the barangay; attending as a mechanism for information-gathering; sustaining continuing dialogue, close coordinating and connecting before the higher levels of the peace and order councils and law enforcement units; monitoring and checking the nefarious activities of criminal elements; ascertaining barangay constituents with strong deviant behavior for referral before the proper authorities; making periodic assessment of the prevailing peace and order situation in their respective areas of responsibility and submitting report with appropriate recommendations before the higher level Peace and Order Council; establishing plans and recommending such measures which will enhance peace and order and public safety in their area of responsibility; and performing such other functions which may be prescribed by upper level peace and order councils.

This study was anchored in the peace, justice and strong institution SDG goals of the United Nation and in the capacity and institutional development agenda of Isabela State University. Particularly, this study is geared headed for measuring the barangay peace and order councils in the preservation of peace and order in Santa Maria, Isabela since this municipality is adopted by College of Criminal Justice Education of Isabela State University for extension programs.

Since the council in the barangay level mainly serves as the bottommost line for planning and implementation of peace and order programs in the community, its evaluation is needed. Likewise, the extent of involvement of the barangay peace and order council in the preservation of peace and order, the functionality level of the Barangay Peace and Order Council, and the satisfaction of the community on the performances of the council can point out the success of the peace and order program of the municipality. Through council assessment, this can be further heightened towards maintaining and reaching community's high level of peace and order.

Recently, there are about 18 crime hotspot barangay in Santa Maria having about 12 index and 43 non-index crimes committed. Meanwhile, some of the responses and capabilities of the Local Government unit in addressing issues on crime is the strengthening of police visibility and establishing task forces involving all barangay officials in the eradicating and solving crimes.

Meanwhile, the output of this study could be significant to the municipal local government unit in assessing their perspective in building a peaceful, progressive community. The study could picture the efforts of the peace and order officers in the ground field supporting the vision and goals of the municipal government; thus, this could be a reference in enacting ordinances to strengthen the community support to the peace and order programs.

The results could be significant to the barangay peace and order councils in measuring how far their programs are working, and likewise, this could be a guide to enhance further and formulate comprehensive peace and order programs for the finest welfares of the community. Besides, the finding of this survey could be used for extension collaboration between Isabela State University-Cabagan and the local government unit of Santa Maria, Isabela.

II. METHODOLOGY

Using descriptive design, this study employed sixty barangay peace and order council members and eighty residents of Santa Maria, Isabela. Arithmetic mean was used to figure out the operation of the barangay peace and order council covering the functionality of the council, participation of the council sectors, implementation of the peace and order ordinances, and the satisfaction of the community on the performances of the peace and order council.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

A. The Functionality of the Barangay Peace and Order Council (BPOC).

Table 1 Level of Functionality of the BPOC

Functionality of BPOC	Mean	Interpretation
1. Organization	3.24	Moderately functional
2. Meetings	3.18	Moderately functional
3. Policies, Plans and Budget	3.25	Moderately functional
4. Accomplishment	2.96	Moderately functional
Category mean	3.16	Moderately functional

The preceding table reflects that the barangay peace and order council of Santa Maria, Isabela is moderately functional as indicated in the category mean 3.16. This data implies that the mandated functions to include organization; meetings; policies, plans and budget; and accomplishment are met and performed by the council in its operation towards the goal of sustaining peace and order.

B. The Participation of the Council Sectors in the Peace and Order Program.

Table 2 Extent of Participation of the Council Sectors in the Peace and Order Program

Duties of the Peace and Order Committee	Mean	Interpretation
1. Designing of peace and order and public safety plan	3	Moderately participated
2. Monitoring the peace and order programs' implementation on the barangay	3.08	Moderately participated
3. Coordinating the peace and order programs' implementation in the barangay to the municipal level	3.22	Moderately participated
4. Attending as information-gathering mechanism	2.96	Moderately participated
5. Nefarious activities of criminal elements' monitoring	3.04	Moderately participated
6. Reporting of unlawful activities before the higher authorities	3.22	Moderately participated
7. Barangay constituents with strong deviant behaviors' identification	3.4	Participated
8. Referring of identified barangay constituents with strong deviate behavior before the appropriate authorities	2.94	Moderately participated
9. Maintenance of continuous dialogue with the barangay constituents	3.06	Moderately participated
10. Coordinating before the higher levels of the peace and order councils	3.22	Moderately participated
11. Plans to improve the peace and order and public safety in their area of responsibility formulation	3	Moderately participated
12. The operation of all community-based anti-crime movements within the barangay monitoring	3.22	Moderately participated
13. Making periodic assessment of the prevailing peace and order situation of the barangay.	3	Moderately participated
Category mean	3.11	Moderately participated

The foregoing table reveals that the sector of the barangay peace and order council of Santa Maria, Isabela moderately participated in the peace and order programs as indicated in the category mean 3.11. This data entails that the members of the council played significant role in achieving peace and order and have combined forces to the present municipality's peace and order programs wherein each affiliate had performed the delegated duties and responsibilities.

C. The Level of Implementation of Peace and Order Ordinances.

Table 3 The level of Implementation of Peace and Order Ordinances

Peace and Order Ordinances	BPOC	Residents	Overall mean	DI
1. Prohibition of selling of firecrackers.	3.38	2.87	3.13	MI
2. Anti-rabies act	3.42	3.00	3.21	MI
3. Prohibition of littering in public places.	3.24	2.77	3.01	MI
4. Prohibition of the use of plastic bags.	2.64	2.72	2.68	MI
5. Prohibition in possessing deadly weapon in public places of the municipality.	3.32	3.00	3.16	MI
6. Prohibition of vandalism of public and private properties.	2.88	2.85	2.87	MI
7. Prohibitions of stray animals in public places of the municipality.	2.66	2.65	2.66	MI
8. Prohibition of vagrancy in public places.	2.82	2.92	2.87	MI
9. Prohibition of drinking intoxicating beverages in all public places.	2.96	2.88	2.92	MI
10. Prohibition of urinating in any public place not intended for restroom.	2.88	2.69	2.79	MI
11. Implementation of curfew hours for minors.	3.68	2.91	3.30	MI
12. Prohibition of the use of modified muffler for motorcycles.	2.86	2.63	2.75	MI
13. Registration of oplan visa for single motorcycle.	3.04	3.14	3.09	MI
14. Waste management program.	3.12	3.03	3.08	MI
15. Prohibition of vehicle loading and unloading in front of the public market.	2.64	2.92	2.78	MI
16. Prohibition of smoking in public places.	2.5	2.56	2.53	MI
17. Prohibition of minors in driving motor vehicles.	2.64	2.63	2.64	MI
Category mean	2.98	2.83	2.91	MI

The forgoing table discloses that the peace and order ordinances of Santa Maria, Isabela are moderately implemented as shown in the category mean 2.91. This data signifies law enforcers in the municipality are firm in the execution of the various peace and order policies. Moreover, the result entails that the peace and order ordinances are employed as a tool in the preservation of public order and security.

D. The Satisfaction of the Community on the Performances of the Barangay Peace and Order Council.

Table 4 The Level Satisfaction of the Community on the Performances of the Barangay Peace and Order Council.

Activities Prescribed in the Barangay Public Safety Plan	Mean	Interpretation
1. Enact barangay peace and order ordinances	3.33	Satisfied
2. Implement barangay peace and order ordinances	3.29	Moderately Satisfied
3. Conduct of regular ronda	2.92	Moderately Satisfied
4. Construct mobile barangay police outpost	2.86	Moderately Satisfied
5. Impose curfew to minors	2.83	Moderately Satisfied
6. Deploy barangay tanods in school premises	2.83	Moderately Satisfied
7. Information gathering on suspected illegal activities	2.95	Moderately Satisfied
8. Campaign against criminality	2.97	Moderately Satisfied
9. Maintain information drop box	2.65	Moderately Satisfied
10. Update list of inhabitants	2.76	Moderately Satisfied
11. Train lupon tagapamayapa	3.00	Moderately Satisfied
12. Computerization of complaints filed	2.83	Moderately Satisfied
13. Deploy barangay tanods to monitor threats within the barangay	2.86	Moderately Satisfied
14. Establish intelligence gathering mechanism	2.92	Moderately Satisfied
15. Education campaign on public safety	3.14	Moderately Satisfied
Category mean	2.94	Moderately Satisfied

The preceding table presents that the residents of Santa Maria, Isabela are moderately satisfied on the performances of the barangay peace and order council as reflected in the category mean 2.94. This result magnifies that the council has justly performed prescribed duties and responsibilities in the preservation of peace and order which delighted the civic clients.

IV. CONCLUSION

In view of the aforementioned findings, it can be concluded that the Barangay Peace and Order Council of Santa Maria, Isabela operates as a machinery for the preservation of peace and order having a standard functional organization and participative members. Moreover, the enactment of peace and order ordinances serves as a tool of the council in its operations to ensure public safety and due to the substantial public safety activities, the community residents are justly delighted to the performances of the peace and order council.

This inquiry focused on the barangay peace and order council, hence future studies may look into the operations of other bodies such as the disaster risk reduction management, katarungang pambarangay, and anti-illegal drugs council.

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